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Human resource function in the strategy process: A case for convergence

Abstract

The future of human resource management (HRM) as a discipline and as a profession is closely tied to the role played by the HRM function in the organizational strategy process. Though the debate on HRM and HRM function continues, some important issues have not been given adequate attention it deserves. First, the credibility of a management idea is partly determined by its diffusion across the world; such credibility will be enhanced if the idea is viewed as applicable in various contexts. This issue led to raise the first research question: (1) to what extent does HRM function play a significant role in the organizational strategy process in Sri Lankan companies? The second issue pertains to how (if at all) modern approaches associated with HRM manage to find their way to Sri Lanka. Here, the debate on convergence versus divergence in management practices and the role of Multi-National Companies (MNCs) and other drivers of globalisation are explored. Thus, (2) to what extent can MNCs and other drivers of globalization play a part in the convergence of HRM practices? The research is guided by four hypotheses. The answers to the two questions were sought from a sample of 78 HR managers in three categories of Sri Lankan manufacturing companies. The findings of the investigation led to the argument that the transfer of HRM practices and philosophies cannot be solely attributed to MNCs and other drivers of globalization, such as efficient communication systems, information technology, ISO standards, and international and professional institutions. The strength of the current local management practices and cohesion of institutions in Sri Lanka, which is arguably due to the colonial legacy and the beginning of unequal interactions with the West, has also played a major role.

Keywords: Strategic management, strategic human resource management, strategic planning, convergence of management practices.

1. Introduction

Organizations have recognised the importance of adopting a wider organizational perspective and accepting HRM as an important part of the organizational strategy process in achieving objectives (Bamberger and Meshoulam, 2000; Barney and Wright, 1998; Boxall and Purcell, 2003; Holbeche, 2001; Schuler and Jackson, 1999). It is emphasised that human resource (HR) practices can help to create a source of sustained competitive advantage, especially when they are aligned with competitive strategies (Butler et al 1991; Cappelli and Singh, 1992; Jackson and Schuler, 1995; Schuler, 1992; Wright and McMahan, 1992). As evidence abounds on the contribution of HRM to organizational outcomes, the debate also continues on the impact of

HRM function on organizational strategy (Akuratiyagamage, 2004; Caldwell, 2003; Sission, 2001; Torrington, 1999). When the significance of the HRM function in the strategy process is considered, two questions have to be answered: what is the importance of the HRM function in the organizational strategy process? And what is the importance of HR managers in the strategy process? Clarifications for these could provide specific suggestions on how to improve the role of HR managers and their departments (Caldwell, 2003; Mamman and Akuratiyagamage, 2005; Mendenhall et al, 2003).

It is also argued that globalization has further strengthened the debate on the significance of HRM in achieving multi-national companies' (MNCs) objectives and created new roles for the HRM function and HR managers in the strategy process (Mendenhall et al, 2003; Schuler et al, 2004; Sparrow, 2002; Sparrow et al, 2004). In this regard, convergence versus divergence in management practices and the role of MNCs and other drivers of globalisation have to be explored. It is accepted that the credibility of a management idea is partly determined by its diffusion across the world; such credibility will be enhanced if the idea is viewed as applicable in various contexts.

In the above context, the paper investigates two issues on “HRM function in the strategy process”. The first issue – the role HRM function plays in the strategy process- led to raise the first research question: (1) to what extent does HRM function play a significant role in the organizational strategy process in Sri Lankan companies? The second issue - convergence versus divergence in management practices and the role of MNCs and other drivers of globalisation in the diffusion of HRM practices across the world – raised the second research question: (2) to what extent can MNCs and other drivers of globalisation be attributed to play a part in the convergence of HRM practices? This pertains to how (if at all) modern approaches associated with HRM manage to find their way to Sri Lanka. These are important issues that have not been given adequate attention it deserves, especially in the Sri Lankan context.

2. Related literature and hypotheses

2.1. Importance of the HRM function and HR managers in the strategy process

It is accepted that HRM practices can be either influenced by strategy or vice versa (Hendry, 1995). First, organizational plans impact directly upon HRM in its role in getting, keeping, developing, and managing people (Hendry, 1995). It is also possible that HRM practices can influence strategy selection and planning, such as whether to grow by developing internally or by acquiring from other firms (Napier, 1996). Thus, HRM function can provide input concerning the availability of the required human resource (quantity, quality, and skill mix) and the costs of acquiring, retaining, developing, and motivating it, indicating that successful business strategies are developed around the “core competencies” or the skills of the organization (Dyer, 1986; 1988). Second, HRM practices implicitly or explicitly create characteristic organizational cultures and reinforce one another insofar as they support a particular culture (Hendry, 1995). Third, strategic plans and strategic decisions depend on the quality of management and the organizational decision-making processes. Human resource management function contributes to the quality of management through management selection and development over time (Hendry, 1995). Therefore, as organizational strategy and HR strategy are both inputs to and a constraint to each other, an important place should be given to the HRM strategy in the organizational strategy process (Wright and Ferris, 1996). However, a number of reasons are responsible for the failure of the HRM component in the strategy

process. The study of Hegarty and Hoffman (1987) revealed that whilst a number of functions influenced strategic decisions, the HRM function consistently exercised the least influence. Further, although organizations were likely to employ HRM specialists and have a range of HRM policies, there was little interconnection between them; also, there was little interconnection with business planning (Storey, 1993).

When considering the role of HR managers in the strategy process, the ability of the HR managers to add value in determining the strategic direction of the corporation, with particular focus on HRM issues, is very important. They have to be active in the strategy process - they have to participate in the organizational decision-making process; they have to make suggestions relating to human resources. On the other hand, their suggestions have to be taken into account and, if valuable, be included in the organizational decisions. Although it is important for HR managers to be actively involved in Board-level decision-making and the HRM function to be consulted on corporate strategy from the outset, Budhwar and Sparrow (1997) revealed inadequate representation of HR managers at the Board level in India. In this context, Devanna et al (1984) argued that the degree of participation of HR managers in the strategy process mainly depends on the extent to which top management is willing to share decision-making through the organization. Kydd and Oppenheim (1990) also argued that in the “proactive” orientation, HR managers should have a seat at the strategic table and they should actively engage in the strategy formulation. In the “reactive” orientation, on the other hand, corporate and business-level strategies ultimately determine HRM policies and practices. Once the business strategy is determined, without the involvement of HR managers, HRM policies and practices are implemented to support the chosen competitive strategy. Despite HR managers’ real and potential contributions, many have yet to acquire the respect and recognition of other departments (Megginson et al, 2004). Tichy et al (1984) found that both HR managers and strategic planners see a need to use more HR data in the strategy formulation. However, few have successfully carved out an appropriate role for their HRM functions. On the other hand, Purcell and Ahlstran (1994) found that HRM issues are “rarely taken into account” in the formulation of corporate strategies. Further, Downie and Coates (1994) found that Canadian HR managers are often outside the decision-making circle. Hence, explanations for the actual status and the contribution of HR managers have to be sought within their own organizations.

2.2. Convergence in HRM practices

Companies are continually striving to gain access to new markets and new supply sources, to capitalise on technology, to utilise assets better, to reduce manufacturing costs, and to become more profitable. One of the ways that can be used to achieve such objectives is international business. Hence, motives for forming international businesses in developing countries, the benefits they provide to local and foreign partners, and their importance at the micro and macro levels are well-documented (Griffith et al, 2001). International business is perceived as a means of knowledge transfer (Child, 1994; Child and Rodrigues, 1996) and they provide a platform for organisational learning, giving access to skills and capabilities of partners (Makhija and Ganesh, 1997; Schuler, 2001). When international business replicates partner experiential knowledge in a jointly owned organisation, one or all partners may have access to knowledge that would not be available in the absence of collaboration (Inkpen and Dinur, 1998; Jayasena et al., 2005). While firms can learn from the other partner, for example, knowledge about its products, technologies, and even the process of forming and maintaining a joint venture, they

can also learn about the other partner, for example, its culture, management style, goals, and values (Schuler, 2001).

Literature suggests that there are a number of different and equally successful ways of organising management in the market economy (Chen, 1995; Whitley, 1994). When companies locate their businesses abroad, they retain and transfer the unique sets of management practices to which they are accustomed. This is reflected in specific management structures, decision-making processes, etc (Akuratiyagamage, 2003; Sparrow et al, 2000). For instance, in studying joint venture management in China, Child (1994) identifies three types of learning and change. The first level is the technical, which involves the acquisition and implementation of new techniques such as total quality management and market forecasting. The second level is the systematic, which refers to the introduction of and operation of new systems and procedures, such as production control and budgeting systems. The third level is the strategic, which concerns the mindsets of senior managers, their criteria of business success, and their understanding of significant factors for achieving success. Although there has been much scholarly and popular debate on the transfer of management practices in the context of Europe, America, and China, less attention has been paid to Asian countries (Cunningham et al, 1996; Taylor, 2001). Specifically, no such studies have been conducted in the context of Sri Lanka, where international business operations have been increasing. As Ding (2000) argued, one would expect some degree of convergence in management practices across the Sri Lankan organizations. This is particularly the case for the selection of the sample from the Sri Lankan Export-oriented Clothing Manufacturing (ECM) industry, given that they are all exporting companies facing similar challenges and dealing with similar markets.

2.3. The context of the study

2.3.1. Export-oriented clothing manufacturing industry

Sri Lanka, being under Western rule for several centuries, faces severe challenges in the sphere of industrialisation, like its other counterparts in the developing world. In the pursuit of industrialisation, the country is left with few options to survive and thrive in a more complex and unpredictable global situation. With high unemployment and insufficient indigenous capital, the attraction of foreign investment becomes a major priority (Central Bank of Sri Lanka, 1998). In response to several factors such as increasing global competition, lower labour costs in Sri Lanka, and inducements from the Sri Lankan government, the number of international businesses coming into Sri Lanka has been increasing since 1977.

The period after the late 1970s saw a rapid expansion in the Export-Oriented Clothing Manufacturing (ECM) Industry in Sri Lanka. The impressive growth witnessed in the ECM industry during this period can be attributed to two major factors. The first is the market-oriented liberal economic policies introduced in 1977. The second is the Multi-Fibre Agreement (MFA) that granted export quotas to developing countries, by guaranteeing export markets (Karunatilake, 1999). A significant feature of the international clothing manufacturing industry after the introduction of MFA is “quota hopping” foreign investments, i.e., relocation of production facilities into the quota available in developing countries. Sri Lanka is one of the countries that benefited from the “quota hopping” investments, with the introduction of market-oriented liberal economic policies in 1977. The overseas manufacturers of clothing from both East Asia (Hong Kong, Taiwan, South Korea, and Singapore) and Europe (Germany, the UK) have relocated their production facilities to Sri Lanka. While the East Asian producers have

moved their operations mainly as a means of “quota hopping”, European producers have moved their operations due to rising production costs in their home countries (Karunatilake, 1999). In the circumstances, investment by East Asian and European manufacturers fuelled the growth of the Sri Lankan ECM industry. At present, apart from the wholly locally owned companies, several ECM companies have been set up in Sri Lanka as wholly foreign-owned companies or as local and foreign joint venture companies.

2.3.2. Planning and HRM in Sri Lanka

Literature provides evidence of the place given to strategic planning and HRM function in the Sri Lankan organizations. Some studies claim a lack of planning in both public and private sectors. For instance, a study conducted in 1982 on the Sri Lankan public sector revealed that planning was not considered a prerequisite to success (Nanayakkara, 1992). According to Nanayakkara (1992), the private sector was no exception. The predominant tendency was to focus on the short run with a view to recovering investment as early as possible. By doing so, the necessary bases for long-term development were undermined or destroyed as the tendency was to achieve the minimum as required by the short-run perspective. In another instance, in an effort to promote industrial investment, Central Bank of Sri Lanka surveyed 5426 private organizations in 1984, and found that half of the private sector organizations studied did not plan at all: nearly one third had a planning horizon of one to two years and about one tenth had a planning horizon of over four years (Nanayakkara, 1992). The reasons given were insufficiency of resources, uncertainty of the market for products, and problems of obtaining credit. Further, the study by Wijesiriwardana (1994) revealed that private sector organizations did not have formal HR policies. It was argued that though steps had been taken under the liberalised economic policies by professional bodies to popularise concepts of strategic planning, it has not been widely practised in Sri Lanka (Jayasena et al., 2005). When systematic long-term planning was foreign to management thinking at the organizational level, it was too foreign at the departmental level (Nanayakkara, 1992).

However, there is some positive evidence for the realization of the importance of the HRM function at the corporate level (Akuratiyagamage, 2005). These reveal that changes that occurred in the Sri Lankan business environment made it clear that organizations have to pay a greater degree of attention to HRM in the total organizational process. According to Jayaratna (1996), many organizations brought in HR managers to corporate management. Further, Gunawardana (1999) suggests that attitudes to HRM are somewhat different in the foreign-owned clothing manufacturing companies. They have started to develop human resources, having identified it (HR) as a key to improvements in the industry. It has also been observed that with the establishment of a considerable number of wholly foreign-owned companies and local and foreign Joint venture companies, new systems of labour relations and work ethics have been "imported", which were alien to the indigenous industrial setup of the country (Tennekoon, 1999). Therefore, it is reasonable to assume that apart from the contribution made by foreign investors to the economic growth of the country, they have brought into Sri Lanka not only modern plants and equipment, but also advanced management expertise and HRM systems and practices.

2.4. Hypotheses

The study is guided by four hypotheses. The hypotheses are based on the general assumption that, because foreign companies will try to adhere to specific sets of practices to which they are accustomed wherever they go, there will be significant differences across ownership types regarding the importance given to HRM function in the organizational strategy process, as well as the contribution of HR managers in the strategy process. To the extent that the set of hypotheses is supported, other things being equal, we would argue that MNCs and globalization have not succeeded in achieving total convergence of management practices.

Hypothesis 1: Wholly foreign-owned companies will give higher importance to the HRM function in the organizational strategy process than that of local and joint venture companies.

Hypothesis 2: Joint venture companies will give higher importance to the HRM function in the organizational strategy process than local companies.

Hypothesis 3: HR managers in wholly foreign-owned companies will contribute more to the strategy process than their counterparts in the local and joint venture companies.

Hypothesis 4: HR managers in joint venture companies will contribute more to the strategy process than their counterparts in the local companies.

3. Methodology

3.1. Population and sample

The ECM companies registered under the Board of Investment of Sri Lanka (BOI) served as the population of the study (BOI, 2000). The sector was chosen because it is central to the government's economic strategy vis-à-vis industrialization and job creation, and the industry is facing similar challenges and dealing with similar markets. At the time of the study, there were 207 (82 local, 68 foreign, 57 joint venture) ECM companies registered under BOI, Sri Lanka. A proportionate stratified random sample of 78 ECM companies was selected (32 local, 26 foreign, 20 joint venture). The number of companies in each category of the sample (local, foreign, joint venture) consisted of more than 35 per cent of the companies in each category of the population.

3.2. Methods of data collection and data analysis

There are several ways of conducting social research, such as experiments, surveys, case studies, histories, and the analysis of archival information. The selection of the research method depends on the purpose and nature of the study. For the investigation, the questionnaire method, complemented with semi-structured interviews, was chosen in order to capture the two dimensions of the investigation. The questionnaire was pilot tested to improve the reliability and face validity of the instrument. A self-administered questionnaire was designed and administered to HR managers of the stratified, randomly selected sample of 78 companies. Semi-structured interviews were deemed necessary to complement the survey questionnaire. A

survey interview guide was developed to corroborate the information that had been gathered from the survey questionnaire and to elaborate on the field by exploring a greater variety of experiences offered by HR managers. 18 HR managers (7 local, 6 foreign, 5 joint venture) from the stratified, randomly selected sample willingly agreed to participate in the interviews.

The data was analysed using SPSS software. Other than descriptive statistics, analysis of variance (ANOVA) between subjects is used to test the hypotheses at the significance level of 0.05.

4. Results

4.1. The role played by the HRM function in the organizational strategy process

4.1.1. Existence of strategic perspective

The first research question is raised as to what extent the HRM function plays a significant role in the organizational strategy process in the Sri Lankan companies. In answering this, the first investigated whether companies have a strategic perspective. The results are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Existence of Strategic Perspective

Existence	Organizational Strategy				HRM Strategy				HRM Policies			
	T	L	F	JV	T	L	F	JV	T	L	F	JV
Yes, Written	47	41	39	70	45	35	46	60	45	31	42	70
Yes, Unwritten	28	28	31	25	25	41	12	15	30	41	23	20
Currently Developing	17	25	16	5	21	19	20	25	19	22	23	10
No, do not have	8	6	14	00	9	5	22	00	6	6	12	00
Total	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100

To the nearest round-off number.

T= % within Total sample, L= % within Local, F= % within Foreign, JV= % within Joint venture

As shown in Table 1, it was revealed that seventy-five per cent of the companies have organizational strategies, seventy per cent of the companies have HRM strategies, and seventy-five per cent of the companies have HRM policies. This can be interpreted to mean that the companies have a strategic perspective. Though data reveals that the majority of companies do have a strategic perspective, a considerable number of companies affirmed that they maintain organizational strategies, HRM strategy, and HRM policies unwritten. This implies a considerable degree of scope and opportunity to develop and strengthen the strategic dimension of their companies.

During the visits to the companies, the researcher had the opportunity to examine internal company documents relating to the strategic perspective of the companies, which mentioned that they have a strategic perspective. When the place given to HRM in the overall organizational strategy is investigated, companies do emphasise the value of HR and the need

for HRM. For instance, the following are two extracts of organizational strategy documents of a joint venture company and a local company.

“...To be an employer of choice by nurturing our people through T&D programmes to realise their fullest potential. We seek to inculcate an environment of openness and innovation as an integral part of the company culture, recognising and rewarding performance...”

Source: Internal document from Joint Venture Company “A.”

“... HR department should create a strategy and needs to be consistent with it. HR department’s strategy should be in line with the company strategy and with other departments’ strategy; HR department has to play a very supportive role when they make decisions with other departments.”

Source: Internal document from Local Company “A.”

The following is from an extract of an HRM strategy document of a foreign company. This expresses the underlying purpose of the HRM function.

“Our main objective is to ensure that effective and efficient utilisation of HR to accomplish the goals and objectives of the organisation. We believe that our success will be determined by our valuable employees.”

Source: Internal document from Foreign Company “A.”

The following are two extracts of HRM policy documents on HRD of a local company and a joint venture company.

“It is the policy of the company to ensure, so far as is reasonably practicable, to provide climate and resources that will enable all employees to advance on merit as far as their talents and skills will take them ...”

Source: Internal document from Local Company “B.”

“Our company is committed to the development of all employees. We believe our employees require needs-based T&D to achieve the mutual objectives of the company and the employees. This process will lead us to develop potential employees in the most desirable direction of his/her career path, aiming at providing opportunities for advancement while ensuring that current and future needs of the organisation are also fulfilled.”

Source: Internal document from Joint Venture Company “B.”

However, these findings are not consistent with earlier studies conducted in Sri Lanka (Nanayakkara, 1992; Wijesiriwardana, 1994). However, it is worth noting that none of these studies were conducted in the ECM industry.

4.1.2. The importance given to the HRM function in the strategy process

As per the first objective, it is investigated whether companies give an important place to the HRM function in the organizational strategy process. The findings are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Importance given to the HRM Function in the Strategy Process

Item	Total sample	Local	Foreign	Joint venture	F	Sig.
Importance given	3.115	3.16	2.96	3.25	0.455	0.636

5=Very High, 1=Very Low.

The first and second hypotheses predicted that wholly foreign-owned companies and joint venture companies would give higher importance to the HRM function in the strategy-making process than local companies would give. But wholly owned foreign companies are more likely to give the highest importance across the companies of different ownership. As can be seen in Table 2, the two hypotheses have not been supported by the data ($F=0.455$; $p 0.636$). However, the mean values shown in Table 2 do not show a high level of importance given to the HRM function in the strategy process by all companies, irrespective of their ownership type. This situation could be explained using two contrasting views. First, with the globalisation of business, the need to improve the company's status will become imperative for the survival of the ECM companies. When systematic planning has not become foreign to management thinking at the organizational level of the ECM companies, it will not be foreign at the departmental level, either. Hence, the status of the HRM function in an organization is expected to improve further. The second explanation would be that, as the industry itself is known as a “footloose industry”, when profits began to decrease, business operations could be shifted to other countries where investors can maximise their profits. As Purcell (1995) argued, this could drive out long-term HRM investment at the workplace and “destroy” the basis of HRM as a part of the corporate strategy. In this context, it is not that the importance given to the HRM function in the strategy process is low, but that its purpose and connection with the wider organizational role are not well established.

4.1.3. Contribution made by HR managers to the organizational strategy process

As per the first objective, an investigation is made to find the contribution made by HR managers to the organizational strategy process. The findings are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: HR Managers' Contribution to the Strategy Process

Item	Total sample	Local	Foreign	Joint venture	F	Sig.
Participate in the company decision-making process	3.63	3.53	3.65	3.75	0.186	0.830
Contribute to company decision-making	3.32	3.19	3.42	3.40	0.355	0.702
Acceptance of HR manager's proposals at the strategy level	3.31	3.16	3.31	3.55	0.909	0.407

5=Always, 1=Never.

Hypotheses 3 and 4 predicted that HR managers in wholly foreign-owned companies and joint ventures would be more likely to be involved in decision-making than their counterparts in the local companies. But HR managers in wholly foreign-owned companies are more likely to experience the highest involvement across companies of different ownership. As can be seen in Table 3, the data do not support the hypotheses. Thus, although the direction of the mean

scores is in line with what has been predicted, the degree of differences in the mean scores is not statistically significant across the companies of different ownership [(F = 0.186; *p* 0.830); (F=0.355; *p* 0.702); (F=0.909, *p* 0.407)].

In the 78 companies studied, the majority of the HR manager posts are held by people with specialised qualifications and experience related to HRM. In fact, sixty-four per cent had professional qualifications in the field of HRM. Forty-five per cent had a degree or a postgraduate degree. Almost all HR managers interviewed felt that it is important to have HR specialists on the Board to participate in the development of corporate strategy and HRM policies. Most of the HR managers interviewed were actually involved in the development of the corporate strategy from the outset. Further, they were involved in a consultative capacity at the implementation stage of new projects or company extension programmes. However, it is revealed that some of the companies are driven by top-down as opposed to bottom-up decision-making. In the latter, HRM functions play a central and influential role in HR decision-making, such as selection, appraisal, reward, and training and development. However, it is revealed during the interviews that in both of these decision-making systems, HR managers had played a proactive role; they had not found any difficulty in performing their roles due to the non-existence of explicit written corporate strategies and HRM policies to refer to. As noted earlier, forty-seven per cent of the responding companies claimed to have written corporate strategies, and forty-five per cent of the responding companies claimed to have written HRM policies (see Table 1). However, by considering overall responses, it is evident that HR managers' contribution within the companies has to be further improved.

4.2. Can MNCs and other drivers of globalization play a part in the convergence of HRM practices?

Analysis of the variance across companies of different ownership did not provide evidence to support all hypotheses. There is no significant difference between local companies and MNCs regarding the importance given to the HRM function as perceived by the HR managers. Similarly, there is no significant difference between local companies and MNCs regarding the contribution of HR managers in the strategy process. The majority of the HR managers revealed that they always participate in the strategy-making process; they contribute to decision-making at the Board level; and their contributions are frequently accepted by the Board level. Therefore, regarding the involvement of HR managers in decision-making, it can be argued that there is a clear convergence of management practice as perceived by the HR managers surveyed. Regarding the importance given to the HRM function, it is difficult to say categorically without hesitation that there is a convergence. This is because, traditionally, in both developed and developing countries, and indeed in MNCs, the HRM function is not considered with high regard. Therefore, it is perhaps safer to say that the status of HRM function across the organizations has not changed significantly.

Second, the lack of significant differences between local companies and MNCs regarding HR managers' involvement in the decision-making appears to suggest that the transfer of HRM and management practices can be attributed to MNCs and other drivers of globalization. For example, drivers of globalization, such as efficient communication systems, information technology, international and professional institutions, play roles in the transfer of management practices and philosophies. When business systems are competing in world markets, they tend to adapt to dominant patterns in those markets. In this context, when foreign management concepts enter into play in the form of the requirements of foreign buyers and international

standards, those approaches to management have a high degree of legitimacy. These could make foreign investors and foreign joint venture partners lose much in transit to Sri Lanka. Another possible explanation for the similarities across the organizations could be that local companies have to compete internationally and with MNCs, so they have to try to reach the standards of MNCs. The other possible explanation in the specific industry context would be that the global competitive environment in the ECM industry seems to play a far more significant role in policy choices than bringing in home practices to host countries when foreign investors/joint venture partners see their foreign assignments as temporary. The final plausible reason is the country context. The strength of the current local management practices and cohesion of institutions in Sri Lanka, which is arguably due to the colonial legacy and the beginning of unequal interactions with the West, has influenced practices likely to be similar. On the whole, as Kerr et al (1960) and Chen (1995) argued, the causes of the similarities are more likely to be external than the Sri Lankan internal business environment.

5. Conclusion

The central objective of this paper is to answer two research questions: (a) to what extent does HRM function play a significant role in the organizational strategy process in Sri Lankan exporting companies? (b) To what extent can MNCs and other drivers of globalization be attributed to play a part in the convergence of HRM practices? The research is guided by four hypotheses. The hypotheses are based on the assumption that local companies will differ from MNCs in the way they deal with the HRM function.

The findings from the study have revealed some important issues. Firstly, it appears that participation in decision-making does not equate to a favourable perception of the importance given to HRM function in the strategy process. Perhaps the HR managers still feel that they are playing a symbolic role on the Board. However, it can be argued that the fact that they are involved at the Board level at all is a significant improvement, especially in a developing country like Sri Lanka.

However, it should be noted that the tests of the hypotheses are based on the perception of HR managers. Therefore, the validity of the hypotheses rested on the accuracy of the HR managers' perceptions. It could be that the perception of managers from other functional areas might be different from that of HR managers. Further, this study is an exploratory one. Therefore, more in-depth studies are needed to explore the role of HR managers in the strategy process and the role of MNCs in the transfer of HRM across borders.

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